

Welcome to SoldAC Second Newsletter!

SoldAC designs a system to convert CO₂ into ethylene

(1) COMET, (2) LOMARTOV, (3) IREC-CERCA, (4) CNR, (5) UDL, (6) EIM, (7) UEDIN, (8) USTAN

We have been working for 12 months now on the research project to design a new system to convert CO₂ into ethylene. Now, all the components that make up the SoldAC system are being elaborated, including the infrastructure for the collection of sunlight, the supply of cold light, and the production and storage of thermal energy. The project, funded by the European Commission (GA 101069359) and Innovate UK (ISF 10039331-10038044), will invest 3 million euros in the design of this new system to convert CO₂ into ethylene.

In this next stage, we are moving on to the phase of studying the requirements needed for each component for its final assembly at the University of Lleida. Therefore... make sure to catch the up-to-date news!

- Full name: Full Spectrum Solar Direct Air Capture and Conversion
- Acronym: SoldAC
- Number of partners: 8
- Start date: 1 September 2022
- Duration: 36 months
- Total budget: 3 M €
- EC funding: 2 M €
- UKRI funding: 1 M €
- Partners acronyms: COMET, LOMARTOV, IREC-CERCA, CNR, UDL, EIM, UEDIN, USTAN

Check out the website: www.soldac-project.eu

At the SoldAC website, you can find all the information about the project.

- Objectives & impacts
- Lab testing
- Consortium
- News & Events
- Publications & Results

SoldAC Project Stakeholders Analysed in Engaging Participatory Workshop

During the General Assembly of the project, held in Edinburgh September 6-7th 2023, the SoldAC project team had the second Responsible Research and Innovation internal workshop. Under the moderation of LOMARTOV, this session was centred in analysing in detail the stakeholder groups of the project with the aim to better align the engagement strategy and the social acceptance of the solutions developed.

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SoldAC 1st Workshop on Direct Air Capture, Storage and Conversion

On September 5th, the first SoldAC Workshop took place under the umbrella of the Heat Powered Cycles Conference 2023. In this edition, the conference dedicated a special Workshop to DAC concepts for carbon storage and conversion, with the aim of boosting R&D and fostering the meeting between experts as well as the creation of networks for future work.

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SoldAC 2nd GA in Edinburgh: Work is progressing with the support of the whole consortium

UEDIN, one of the SoldAC project partners, meets the University of Technology and Applied Sciences (UTAS), one of the most lively and fast-growing higher education institutions in Oman.

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Capturing CO₂ from the atmosphere without effort

The first General Assembly was held at the UPC Campus Diagonal Besòs facilities and was hosted by IREC-CERCA. It was a great opportunity to meet and exchange knowledge of the different units that are part of the overall system.

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Meet Our Partners

IREC Interview

Sebastián Murcia
IREC

[▶ WATCH NOW](#)

Past events

SoldAC project connected with the main actors in public perception assessment of carbon capture technologies [▶ LEARN MORE](#)

Participation of the University of Edinburgh in Electrochem 2023 [▶ LEARN MORE](#)

First SoldAC Workshop in the Heat Powered Cycles in Edinburgh 2023 [▶ LEARN MORE](#)

Upcoming events

MATSUS (Barcelona, 4th-8th March) [▶ LEARN MORE](#)

Carbon Capture Summit (Amsterdam, 3rd-5th June) [▶ LEARN MORE](#)

Carbon Capture Technology Expo (23rd-24th October) [▶ LEARN MORE](#)

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<https://soldac-project.eu/>

Coordinator :

Partners :

Associated partners :

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Innovate UK

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